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ICanRead: A Needs-Based Reading Intervention Program for Grade 3 Pupils

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Abstract: This paper aimed at developing and validating a reading intervention program for Grade 3 readers. The ICanRead program includes the essential components of reading like word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension through a series of 45-minute individualized instruction for five (5) days a week for one and a half months. These elements are integrated within the three main parts of the program: Get Ready, Read Aloud, and Reading Skills Boost. Experts validated the program and then tried it out on the student participants and evaluated its effectiveness afterwards. The positive results of trying out the program suggest that 1) reading intervention programs help struggling readers to cope and progress in reading; 2) struggling readers may have different needs according to the skills where the child demonstrates difficulty, may it be with word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension, or a combination of these areas; 3) effective reading intervention programs should be designed and developed according to the specific needs of a particular struggling reader; and 4) the teacher's explicit scaffolding is essential for the students to achieve reading proficiency.

Keywords: *struggling readers, reading program, needs-based intervention*

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Introduction

Reading is an essential skill everyone must learn. It was even pronounced by the International Literacy Association (ILA, 2019) as a basic human right. People read for many purposes, like to gain knowledge, for entertainment, and even for leisure. Reading is crucial and influential, especially in today's information age (Kim, 2022). Reading also serves as the cornerstone for school-based learning and academic, professional, and vocational success (Lesnick et al., 2010). Reading proficiency is crucial, especially for young children from K-3, as it is the access to all other knowledge. When children read, they can quickly gain an understanding of themselves and the things around them (Neuman et al., 2000).

Reading skills are essentially developed during early childhood years, the period for literacy development (Neuman et al., 2000). It is during these years that most children are “learning to read”. However, in the fourth grade, they are “reading to learn”, using their skills to gain more information, solve problems, think critically, and communicate their learning effectively (Fiester, 2010). It is assumed that after third grade, all students can read skillfully at increasing proficiency level. This critical transition in a child's reading development may lead to their educational success or failure (Lesnick et al., 2010). When students cannot read at grade level by the third grade, they begin to experience difficulty understanding written texts. It could affect their learning in the next grade levels as they meet greater demands in education (Lesnick et al., 2010).

In 2000, the National Reading Panel (NRP) identified critical skills or areas vital to reading success. It was in response to the congressional mandate to assist parents, teachers, and legislators plan and implement effective reading instruction. These are phonemic awareness (the ability to understand that spoken words are made up of sounds), phonics (learning the relationships between written letters and spoken sounds), fluency (reading a text efficiently and accurately), vocabulary (knowing the meaning of words) and comprehension (the ability to understand and remember the text) (Armbruster et al., 2010). Related to this, researchers from various fields proposed that students can experience difficulty in any of the mentioned areas crucial to reading success (ILA, 2019). Therefore, effective and appropriate reading instruction is what addresses the student's individual need/needs based on the different key areas of reading. A one-size-fits-all instruction that is not matched to the student's needs could not be of help (ILA, 2019). Appropriate and needs-based interventions for poor readers will help them succeed in their reading goals and encourage and motivate them to learn and read more. Reading would become more manageable and enjoyable for them (Paul, 2012).

The Study

The purpose of this study was to propose an effective reading intervention program that would cater to the specific needs of students, particularly third graders who experience difficulties in becoming proficient readers.

Methodology

Design

This study followed the Type 1 Developmental Research design proposed by Richey and Klein (2005). Developmental Research is a systematic study of designing, developing, and evaluating instructional programs, processes and products that must meet the criteria of internal consistency and effectiveness (Richey & Klein, 2005). Type 1 studies

may have an analysis phase, design phase, a development phase, and a try-out and evaluation phase. For this study, a reading intervention program specifically for Grade 3 struggling readers was conceptualized, designed and developed, validated, tried out, and evaluated. First, the purpose and framework of the research were conceptualized, and then the data needed to design the reading intervention program were gathered. After the data collection, essential elements and features of the program were completed, including the step-by-step procedure of the implementation part of the program. Experts evaluated the program for face and content validity before its implementation. The program was tried out to the identified struggling readers, and then program evaluation followed.

Participants

The participants in the study were four struggling readers in third grade of the Elementary Department of a private school in Taytay, Rizal, Philippines. These students, two boys and two girls, fell on the Frustration reading level scores of 89% and below in word recognition and 58% and below in comprehension in the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI, 2008) pre-assessment tool. This is the lowest reading level wherein the student makes errors such as reversal, repetition, substitution, insertion, mispronunciation, and inability to interpret punctuation (PHIL-IRI, 2008). The four participants were given pseudonyms in this study. They were Riley, Alphameg, Zeemir, and Martha.

The parents or legal guardians of the student participants were asked to sign and return an informed consent for the children to participate in the research to comply with the law. Both the parents and the students were informed about the study, and they were given the right to refuse to participate if so desired. The parents signed the permission form as they agreed to have their children join the program.

Instrument

The four student participants of the study went through pre-assessments on the five reading elements (phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and text comprehension) to determine their reading levels and areas of difficulty as the basis for the development of the reading intervention program. The instruments for measuring reading levels and reading assessment were the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI, 2008), Fry Sight-Word Inventory, Cloze Test, Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills 6th Edition (DIBELS) Oral Reading Fluency.

The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) aims to define children's reading levels in the elementary grades. It assesses pupils' reading speed and comprehension in oral and silent reading in both English and Filipino (PHIL-IRI Manual and User's Guide, 2018). In this study, PHIL-IRI was utilized to measure the reading speed, word recognition accuracy, and comprehension of the participants in English to determine their reading level: independent, instructional, and frustration.

Other assessment tools were administered to determine the skills where the student participants demonstrated difficulty. Word recognition was assessed through the Fry Sight-Word Inventory. It defines a student's ability or inability to recognize individual words. This list of 600 words compiled by Edward Fry contains the most used words in reading and writing. The comments are divided into six levels, roughly corresponding to grade levels, then into groups of twenty-five words, according to difficulty and frequency.

The cloze test was used in assessing vocabulary skills. The cloze test is based on a text with gaps. The examinee has to complete the gaps with appropriate words. The DIBELS Oral Reading Fluency (DORF) is a standardized, individually administered test of accuracy and fluency with connected text. PHIL-IRI was used to measure the participants' comprehension level.

Three experts were asked to evaluate the reading intervention program for face and content validity. Two of them are taking up Master of Arts in Education with Specialization in Reading, and the other one is an experienced Grade 3 teacher. They were given criteria for the basis of evaluation. The evaluation form includes standards that describe the program: 1) Goals and Objectives, 2) Instructional Programs and Materials, 3) Assessment, and 4) Instructional Time. The experts were requested to rate the reading program with a Yes or No, corresponding evaluation criterion. A column for comments and suggestions and a space for recommendations were also provided.

The student participants took the 20-item multiple choice test on four reading passages before and after the intervention. The test was developed by the researcher, which included questions on word recognition, vocabulary, and comprehension check, and was utilized for the pre- and post-measurement of the study. The texts used were derived from DIBELS Oral Reading Fluency Progress Monitoring Third Grade Student Materials (Good et al., 2007).

The student participants were also requested to evaluate the reading intervention program according to their experience during the program try-out. They were given a form that included descriptive criteria for the try-out evaluation. The evaluation form was developed by the researcher. It consists of the following: 1) Being willing to participate in the program; 2) Attending the reading session regularly with eagerness and joy; 3) Being aware of my reading goals in participating in the program; 4) Setting (location, room) promotes students' engagement for the entire session; 5) The reading activities are appropriate and attainable; 6) The teacher's instructions are clear; 7) Understands the texts and able to answer the questions with confidence; 8) Session length is appropriate; 9) Known to self that there are improvements in one or two reading skills; and 10) Developed the love for reading. The students draw a happy face for 'Yes' and a sad face for a 'No' answer for each criterion.

The parents were asked to evaluate the reading intervention program through an evaluation form developed by the researcher. The evaluation form criteria are: 1) The pupil attends the reading session regularly with eagerness and joy; 2) The pupil shows a willingness to participate in the program; 3) The pupil is aware of their reading goals in participating in the program; 4) Setting (location, room) promotes students' engagement for the entire session; 5) The content is aligned with foundational reading skills for the grade; 6) The text and text complexity are appropriate for the reading level of students; 7) Sufficient amount of time is allocated for instruction and the time allocated is used effectively; 8) The instructional program and materials provide explicit and systematic instruction on critical reading priorities (i.e., word recognition (phonemic awareness, phonics), fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension); 9) The pupil is engaged and responsive, and; 10) Improvements in one or two reading skills are evident on the pupil. The parents were provided copies of the program description as another basis of evaluation. The parents indicated their ratings by checking the number of their corresponding response (Strongly Agree – 4, Agree – 3, Disagree -2, Strongly Disagree – 1) to a criterion.

Data Gathering Procedure

Figure 1 shows the research process which includes the six phases in the conduct of the

study. The specific data gathering procedures were discussed in each phase of the research (Richey & Klein, 2005).

Figure 1

Research Process of the Study

Conceptualization. In this stage, systematic procedure and coordination were done before the conduct of the actual research. In this stage, the purpose and framework of the research were conceptualized. The researcher explored and examined previous literature and studies about reading intervention programs, including designs, content, assessments, and implementation procedures. Findings from the examined related literature and studies were considered in shaping the framework of the reading intervention program.

Data Collection

Determining the reading levels and skills where the student participants demonstrate difficulty was needed in developing the reading intervention program. First, a pre-assessment to identify reading levels was given to the student participants using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI). The PHIL-IRI Oral Test uses a set of criteria in identifying the pupils' reading levels, including the percentage of word recognition accuracy and the percentage of correct answers to comprehension questions. Table 1 shows the Phil-IRI Oral Test criteria (Phil-IRI, 2008).

Table 1

Phil-IRI Oral Test Criteria

Level	Word Recognition (WR)		Comprehension
Independent	97 - 100%	and	80% - 100%
Instructional	90 - 96%	and	59% - 79%
Frustration	89% below	or	58% - below

The reading levels are described in the Phil-IRI Manual as follows:

1. Frustration

- This is the lowest reading level.
- The pupil shows withdrawal from reading situations by crying or refusing to read.
- The pupil commits errors in reading, such as reversal, repetition, substitution, insertion, mispronunciation, and inability to interpret punctuation.
- The pupil scores 89% and below in word recognition or 58% and below in comprehension.

2. Instructional

- It is the level at which the pupil can profit from instruction.
- The pupil's oral reading is rhythmical, with a conversational tone and correct interpretation.
- The pupil scores 90-96% in word recognition and 59%-79% in comprehension

3. Independent

- It is the highest level at which a pupil can read independently and with ease without the help or guidance of the teacher.
- The pupil is free from tension, finger-pointing, or lip movement.
- The pupil reads with rhythm and conversational tone and interprets punctuation correctly.
- The pupils score 97-100% in word recognition and 80%-100% in comprehension.

Tests were administered to assess pupils' reading speed and comprehension in oral and silent reading in English. Each student participant was given a passage for their grade level, and then they were asked to read the passage silently and orally. As the student read the passage orally, errors made were marked. Miscue or error includes mispronunciation, substitution, refusal to pronounce, insertion, omission, repetition, and reversal. Then, the scores for reading speed and word recognition were computed and recorded. For comprehension test, the student participants read the passage silently for 2 minutes, then after reading, comprehension questions were asked. The scores were computed accordingly. Then, the results were used as basis for identifying the reading levels of the pupils (refer to Table 1). Table 2 shows the overall reading ability of each child. The reading intervention program was tried out to the students who fell on the frustration level.

The following are the formulas used in computing the pupils' word recognition and comprehension:

Word Recognition Computation

$$\frac{\text{No. of major miscue (M)}}{\text{No. of words in the passage (N)}} \times 100 = \% \text{ of M}$$

Word Recognition (WR):

$$\% \text{ correct} = 100\% - \% \text{ of M}$$

Comprehension Computation

$$\frac{\text{No. of correct answers}}{\text{No. of questions}} \times 100 = \% \text{ of CR}$$

Comprehension (C):

Table 2

Overall Reading Ability

Word Recognition	Comprehension	Reading Level
Independent	Independent	Independent
Independent	Instructional	Instructional
Independent	Frustration	Frustration

Instructional	Independent	Independent
Instructional	Instructional	Instructional
Instructional	Frustration	Frustration
Frustration	Independent	Frustration
Frustration	Instructional	Frustration
Frustration	Frustration	Frustration

The student participants of the study went through another set of assessments to determine the skills where they found difficulty: word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, or comprehension. A word recognition test was administered using the Fry Sight–Word Inventory. Each student read the words aloud and continued until they made five or more errors in a group of 25 words. This indicates frustration, and instruction should begin on the previous list. The criterion for this is being able to read 100 words in one minute with 95% accuracy in the primary grades. The reading levels could be determined when the student begins to make errors in reading the word lists—using the general criteria for word recognition levels as 95% as independent, 90% as instructional, and less than 90% indicating frustration level. Using DIBELS Oral Reading Fluency, student performance was measured by having students read a passage aloud for 1 minute. Words omitted, substituted, and hesitations of more than 3 seconds are scored as errors. Words self-corrected within 3 seconds are scored as accurate. The number of correct words per minute from the passage is the oral reading fluency rate (Good & Kaminski, 2002). The comprehension level is based on the PHIL-IRI result on the first pre-assessment. The student read the passage silently for 2 minutes, then after reading, comprehension questions were asked. The scores were computed accordingly. Then, the results were used as the basis for identifying the comprehension level of the pupils (refer to Tables 1 & 3).

Development

The design and development of the reading intervention program were based on the assessment results and findings gathered from related works of literature and studies. Essential elements and features of an effective reading intervention program were completed in this stage of the research process, including the step-by-step procedure of the implementation part of the program. The development of the content of the program has the following criteria: time frame, competencies, content/topic, strategies, assessment, and materials.

The Time Frame refers to the schedule of the day and time of the program implementation, whether daily, weekly, or hourly. Included in the Competencies are the desired outcomes or goals for improving reading skills. The Content/Topic is the text or theme used in the program. Strategies are the learning experiences or approaches to achieve the goals or desired outcome, which are the pre-reading, during reading, and post-reading activities. Another essential component is the Assessment, which refers to the instruments and procedures for measuring and evaluating reading achievements and essential skills. Materials are also necessary for the program. The passages used were derived from the Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills (DIBELS) 6th Edition Oral Reading Fluency (DORF) third grade student materials. The DORF standardized passages are based on the Curriculum-Based Measurement of reading by Stan Deno and colleagues at the University of Minnesota (Good & Kaminski, 2002).

The reading intervention program includes activities that follow the elements of an

effective reading instruction (National Reading Panel (NRP), 2000): word recognition instruction (phonics instruction and phonemic awareness instruction), fluency instruction, vocabulary instruction, and text comprehension instruction.

Validation

Before its implementation, the program was evaluated by three experts for face and content validity. The validation form includes criteria that describe the program: 1) Goals and Objectives, 2) Instructional Programs and Materials, 3) Assessment, and 4) Instructional Time. All the experts gave suggestions and comments. Their suggestions were collected and interpreted. Then, revisions were applied based on the recommendations.

Try-Out

The try-out took place inside the Elementary Department library of the school, which was the most appropriate room for the implementation of the study. It was done for 45 minutes daily for five school days of the six-week program implementation. The program was evaluated to determine its effectiveness after the try-out.

Evaluation

Try-out evaluations were accomplished by the four student participants and their respective parents. The evaluation aimed to assess the proposed reading intervention program through the behavior and feedback from the students' and parents' experiences and observations. The parents were provided with copies of the program's description as the basis of evaluation. The criteria were read and explained to the children before marking their forms.

Ethical Practices

To comply with the proper research ethics, proper coordination was done before the conduct of the study. Letters of request were forwarded to the appropriate authorities, like the school principal and the teacher-in-charge, and approval was sought for the administration of the research procedures. Since the study involved minors, parental consent and student assent were obtained before the research study was started. The informed consent form included the essential parts of the form which explained the nature and content of the study. Parents' and students' decisions were recognized and respected. The program results were pooled for the thesis project, and this study's individual results would remain confidential and anonymous. If some participants showed discomfort and did not want to continue to be part of the study, the researcher recognized it and respected the participants' decision. In case the participants were at risk or in danger, relevant authorities would have been notified to save the participants from harm. No costs were incurred by either the school or the student participants. The participants were given tokens and gifts as incentives and as the researcher's way of expressing gratitude to them. The researcher relayed to the parents the results of all the research procedures related to their children.

Data analysis

The raw scores from the research instruments and assessment tools such as the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI), Fry Sight-Word Inventory, Cloze Test, and the Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills (DIBELS) 6th Edition Oral

Reading Fluency for the identification of reading levels and skills where the student participants demonstrate difficulty, and the evaluation of the reading intervention program and the actual try-out were tabulated and interpreted to present the summary and results.

An outcome assessment or measurement was done using the teacher-made 20-item multiple-choice test before and after the treatment. Percentage change was used to measure the gain scores of the students before and after the implementation of the reading intervention program. Through the percentage change, the scores were compared and determined if there was a difference between them and whether there would be an increase or decrease in the scores. A narrative summary was presented to give further description of the results.

Result

This section reports the results of the study and the discussion of the results. The main purpose of the study was to create a reading intervention program that would help Grade 3 struggling readers achieve proficiency in reading. Specifically, the study aimed to identify the specific reading skill/skills where pupils need intervention and to design, develop and evaluate the reading intervention program based on the identified needs.

Identify the specific reading skill/skills where pupils need intervention

Table 3 shows that nine pupils fell at the frustration level, and they were supposed to be the participants of the study. However, only four pupils agreed to participate in the study. They were given pseudonyms in this study: Martha, Riley, Alphameg, and Zeemir. The four pupils took another pre-assessment test to determine their areas of difficulty using the Fry Sight-Word Inventory, Cloze test, and DIBELS Oral Reading Fluency. The Fry Sight-Word Inventory was utilized to determine the student's ability or inability to recognize individual words; the Cloze test was used for vocabulary skill assessment, the DIBELS Oral Reading Fluency for fluency, and PHIL-IRI for comprehension.

Table 3

Pre-Assessment: Identifying the Reading Level (PHIL-IRI)

Name	Word Recognition		Comprehension		Overall Reading Level
	Rate	Level	Rate	Level	
1. Gideon	93%	Instructional	85%	Independent	Independent
2. Martha	87%	Frustration	71%	Instructional	Frustration
3. Riley	57%	Frustration	28%	Frustration	Frustration
4. Raffy	76%	Frustration	71%	Instructional	Frustration
5. Alphameg	76%	Frustration	71%	Instructional	Frustration
6. Neil	86%	Frustration	85%	Independent	Frustration
7. Johanne	81%	Frustration	85%	Independent	Frustration
8. Dolina	92%	Instructional	71%	Instructional	Instructional

9. Carlo	82%	Frustration	71%	Instructional	Frustration
10. Alicia	93%	Instructional	57%	Frustration	Frustration
11. Zeemir	61%	Frustration	42%	Frustration	Frustration

Table 4 shows that Martha got 96% in word recognition, 50% in vocabulary, 99% in fluency, and 71% comprehension. Martha's scores indicate that she can read words quickly and effortlessly with understanding, but her score indicates that vocabulary is a concern for her. She tended to guess the meaning of words and did not use context clues to choose the correct meaning of the words.

Table 4

Pre-Assessment: Determining the Skills Where the Student Participants Demonstrate Difficulty

Name	Fry Sight-Word (Word Recognition)		Cloze Test (Vocabulary)		DORF (Fluency)		PHIL-IRI (Comprehension)	
	Rate	Level	Rate	Level	Rate	Level	Rate	Level
Martha	96%	Instructional	50%	Frustration	99%	Independent	71%	Instructional
Riley	60%	Frustration	33%	Frustration	81%	Frustration	28%	Frustration
Alphameg	80%	Frustration	17%	Frustration	90%	Frustration	71%	Instructional
Zeemir	66%	Frustration	50%	Frustration	83%	Frustration	42%	Frustration

Riley got 60% in word recognition, 33% in vocabulary assessment, 81% in fluency, and 28% in comprehension. Zeemir acquired 66% in word recognition, 50% in vocabulary assessment, 83% in fluency, and 42% in comprehension. Riley's and Zeemir's scores have placed them at the lowest level in all the reading skills. This indicates that both struggled with decoding and recognizing words, accurate and automatic reading, and understanding the text. The two boys have shown similar reading difficulties. They frequently slowed down when trying to sound out words. They committed errors in reading, such as reversal, repetition, substitution, insertion, and mispronunciation. They were unable to interpret punctuation marks correctly, like period (.), question mark (?), and exclamation point (!). They tended to read in a quiet voice. They were monotonic and had a poor recognition of phrase boundaries. They had difficulty remembering information in the article and lacked understanding of story structure.

Alphameg scored 80% in word recognition assessment, 17% in vocabulary assessment, 90% in fluency, and 71% in comprehension. Though she was at the instructional level in comprehension, Alphameg showed weakness in recognizing, understanding, and reading words fluently. Alphameg read the texts with little expression and enthusiasm in her voice. She could not interpret the punctuation marks correctly and even pointed words with her finger when reading. She read with extended pauses, substitutions, frequent repetitions, and hesitations.

Table 5 shows the skills where the student participants need intervention. The scores indicate that Riley's and Zeemir's significant areas of weakness are word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension. Though Alphameg fell on the instructional level in comprehension, she struggled with word recognition, vocabulary, and comprehension. Martha was at frustration level on the vocabulary test, instructional level in word recognition, independent level in fluency, and instructional level in comprehension.

Table 5

Skills Where the Student Participants Demonstrate Difficulty

Name	Skills Where the Student Participants Demonstrate Difficulty
Martha	vocabulary
Riley	word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension
Alphameg	word recognition, vocabulary, fluency
Zeemir	word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension

Design and develop the reading intervention program that will help struggling pupils improve the identified reading skill/skills

The results of the pre-assessment tests were used as the basis for designing and developing the reading intervention program named as ICanRead. It sought to help Riley, Zeemir, and Alphameg recognize and read words automatically, understand words and expand their vocabulary, read words accurately and fluently, and read text with comprehension, and for Martha to be at the independent level on vocabulary skill and for her to improve her word recognition, fluency, and comprehension skills so she would be able to read successfully. For these reasons, ICanRead is a reading intervention program designed for Grade 3 pupils who struggle with reading. It is interactive, literature-based, and student-centered.

Figure 2 shows the framework of the ICanRead Reading Intervention Program. The reading intervention program integrates essential components of reading (word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension) into a 45-minute routine with individualized reading instruction. These elements are integrated within the three main parts of the program, which are Get Ready, Read Aloud, and Reading Skills Boost. The 'Get Ready' part prepares the participants for the session by establishing goals for learning, activating prior knowledge by looking at what is already known about the story or article, and making initial predictions about the text by checking the title, vocabulary, sentence structure, and sequence of information. Next is the 'Read Aloud,' which includes two parts: the 'Read to the Reader,' wherein the story or article is read to the student and events in the story are discussed, and the characters and emotions presented. The second is 'The Reader Reads.' During this time, the student reads the story or article aloud as the teacher listens and records the unknown and difficult words. The third central part of the program is the 'Reading Skills Boost,' wherein the reading skills are being enhanced. Different strategies for word recognition, like sight word

reading, word flashcards, spelling, and cards for games, are being utilized. Vocabulary is expanded through different vocabulary testing techniques like cloze test, matching, sentence completion, odd one out, dictation, and definitions. Echo reading and repeated readings are included for fluency improvement. Reading strategies like summarizing, retelling, answering comprehension questions, recognizing sequence, comparing and contrasting, and identifying and interpreting meaning are employed for comprehension instruction.

Figure 2

ICanRead Reading Intervention Program Framework

ICanRead uses the DIBELS Oral Reading Fluency (DORF) third-grade student materials. The DORF standardized passages are based on the research and development program of Curriculum-Based Measurement of Reading by Stan Deno and colleagues at the University of Minnesota (Good & Kaminski, 2002).

ICanRead is implemented five days a week, for 45 minutes daily for six weeks. These results in 30 intervention sessions per student. It utilizes individualized reading instruction, recognizing its efficacy for struggling readers than using more extensive group instruction (Swanson & Hoskyn, 1998; Vaughn et al., 2000; Scammaca et al., 2007; Eurydice Network, 2011, cited in Nugen et al., 2012).

Figure 3 shows the assessment and instruction procedure of the intervention program. In the first step, the students must undergo pre-assessments on essential reading elements to determine their reading levels (Table 4) and skills where they demonstrate difficulty as the basis of the intervention. The instruments for measuring reading levels and areas of difficulty are the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI, 2008), Fry Sight-Word Inventory, Cloze Test, Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills (DIBELS) 6th Edition Oral Reading Fluency. Further, diagnostic tests and progress monitoring were administered to systematically assess the students' achievements. Word recognition, vocabulary, and comprehension levels were assessed through the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI, 2008) computations (Tables 2 & 3) and sets of criteria. An outcome assessment or measurement was done using the teacher-

made 20-item multiple-choice test before and after the treatment.

Figure 3

Assessment and Instruction Procedure

Evaluate the reading intervention program through experts' validation and try-out.

Experts' Validation

Three experts evaluated and validated the reading intervention program for content and face validity. They validated the reading intervention program with the following criteria (Table 6) that describe the program: 1) Goals and Objectives, 2) Instructional Programs and Materials, 3) Assessment, and 4) Instructional Time.

Table 6

Content and Face Validation

Criteria	Evaluator		
	1	2	3
Goals and Objectives			
Goals and Objectives are clearly defined and measurable at the grade level.	✓	✓	✓
They are prioritized and dedicated to the essential elements (i.e., phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension) in reading.	✓	✓	✓
They guide instructional and curricular decisions (e.g., time allocations, curriculum program adoptions).	✓	✓	✓
Instructional Programs and Materials			

The instructional program and materials provide explicit and systematic instruction on critical reading priorities (i.e. word recognition (phonemic awareness, phonics), fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension).	✓	✓	✓
The text and text complexity are appropriate for the reading level of students.	✓	X	✓
Material cultivates student engagement in reading text carefully.	✓	✓	✓
Material includes questions and tasks that require students to analyze information and evidence focused on the meaning of texts.	✓	✓	✓
The content is aligned with foundational reading skills for the grade.	✓	✓	✓
Assessment			
Instruments and procedures for assessing reading achievement are clearly specified, measure essential skills, provide reliable and valid information about student performance, and inform instruction in important, meaningful, and maintainable ways.	✓	✓	✓
Instructional Time			
A sufficient amount of time is allocated for instruction and the time allocated is used effectively.	✓	X	✓

All the experts gave suggestions and comments, which were taken into consideration for the improvement of the reading intervention program. Positive remarks included were: The goals and objectives suited the needs of the students; The program was very meaningful; It served as a guide to assess learners by their capability to read and to help them improve themselves in reading, and; The goals successfully adapted to the curriculum program design. On the other hand, comments and suggestions were made, such as some passages were not within the schema of the learners, most of the selections included featured complex vocabulary for the target learners, the passages were very difficult for the struggling students to comprehend, short duration of intervention (only six weeks), and goals were immeasurable in 45 minute-sessions.

The researcher reviewed the reading intervention program based on the experts' suggestions and made some improvements. The passages which were not within the context of the learners were removed and replaced with more appropriate texts. The program includes activities and strategies that expand and understand vocabulary words. The passages were relevant to the grade level because they were derived from the Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills (DIBELS) 6th Edition Oral Reading Fluency (DORF) third-grade student materials, which are standardized based on the program of research and development of Curriculum-Based Measurement of reading. The researcher maintained the duration of the reading intervention program, which is six weeks and 45 minutes daily in five days. It is based on the concept of 'little and often' (Rose, 2009, as cited in Nugent et al., 2012), wherein short and intensive interventions,

with daily, targeted support, appear to be more effective than longer-term interventions (Nugent et al., 2012).

Try-Out

The proposed reading intervention program was tried on four third-grade students from a private school in Taytay, Rizal, namely Riley, Alphameg, Zeemir, and Martha. These four student participants were assessed and identified to have difficulty in the different reading skills: Martha on vocabulary, Alphameg on word recognition, vocabulary, and fluency, Riley and Zeemir on word recognition, vocabulary, fluency, and comprehension. The try-out was done to evaluate the efficacy of the program in helping the struggling readers gain proficiency in reading. The try-out was held from April 9, 2018 to May 18, 2018, five times a week for 45 minutes each session. The study was conducted for a total of 6 weeks and resulted in 30 sessions of intervention per student. The intervention was implemented through individualized instruction. The researcher-facilitator implemented the instructional practices/activities indicated in the reading intervention program for each session, including Get Ready, Read Aloud, and Reading Skills Boost. The students took the 20-item multiple choice test on four reading passages before and after the intervention. It included questions on word recognition, vocabulary, and comprehension checks and was utilized for the pre and post-measurement of the study.

The results of the pre and post-measurements of the study shown in Tables 7, 8, 9, and 10 were computed using the percentage change formula to determine if there was progress in the participants' reading skills through their scores that could help evaluate the efficacy of the ICanRead intervention program. The results of the computations are not intended to show statistical significance since the sample size is too small, and it is designed specifically for this study only.

Table 7

Word Recognition

<i>Name</i>	<i>Before Treatment</i>		<i>After Treatment</i>		<i>Percentage Change</i>
	<i>Score Percentage</i>	<i>in Level</i>	<i>Score Percentage</i>	<i>in Level</i>	
Riley	89.3	Frustration	95.9	Instructional	6.6 % increase
Alphameg	87.7	Frustration	97	Independent	9.3 % increase
Zeemir	82.1	Frustration	98	Independent	15.9 % increase
Martha	94.4	Instructional	100	Independent	5.6 % increase

Table 8

Comprehension

Name	Before Treatment		After Treatment		Percentage Change
	Score in Percentage	Level	Score in Percentage	Level	
Riley	80	Independent	100	Independent	20 % increase
Alphameg	100	Independent	100	Independent	-
Zeemir	60	Instructional	100	Independent	40 % increase
Martha	100	Independent	100	Independent	-

Table 9

Vocabulary

Name	Before Treatment		After Treatment		Percentage Change
	Score in Percentage	Level	Score in Percentage	Level	
Riley	80	Independent	100	Independent	20% increase
Alphameg	80	Independent	100	Independent	20% increase
Zeemir	80	Independent	100	Independent	20% increase
Martha	100	Independent	100	Independent	-

Table 10

Fluency

Name	Before Treatment		After Treatment		Percentage Change
	Score in Percentage	Level	Score in Percentage	Level	
Riley	89.2	Frustration	94.8	Instructional	5.6 % increase
Alphameg	89	Frustration	95.8	Instructional	6.8 % increase
Zeemir	83.6	Frustration	98.5	Independent	14.9 % increase
Martha	94	Instructional	100	Independent	6 % increase

Table 11

One Minute Probe- words correct per minute (WCPM)

Student Name	Fluency (One Minute Probe- words correct per minute (WCPM))		WCPM Growth
	Before Treatment	After Treatment	
Riley	25	55	30
Alphameg	81	93	12
Zeemir	41	67	26
Martha	85	120	35

A one-minute fluency assessment was also conducted as the students read the passage on fluency before and after the intervention. The students' scores are shown in Table 11:

Riley got a WCPM growth of 30; Alphameg got an increase of 12; Zeemir had a 26 WCPM increase; and Martha 35. The scores show that the students improved their reading fluency as their scores got higher after the treatment.

The four student participants and their respective parents also accomplished the try-out evaluation. Tables 12 and 13 present the students' and parents' try-out evaluation results. The students draw a happy face (😊) for a 'yes' and a sad face (😞) for a 'no.' The parents indicated their ratings by checking the number of their corresponding responses (Strongly Agree – 4, Agree – 3, Disagree -2, Strongly Disagree – 1) to a criterion. All the four students marked all the criteria with a 'yes' (😊). The parents checked #4, expressing strong agreement with all the requirements in their evaluation form.

Table 12

Students' Try-out Evaluation

Criteria	Pupil				% of Yes	% of No
	1	2	3	4		
1. Willing to participate in the program.	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
2. Attends the reading session regularly with eagerness and joy.	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
3. Aware of my reading goals in participating in the program.	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
4. Setting promotes students' engagements for the entire session (location, room)	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
5. The reading activities are appropriate and attainable	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
6. The teacher's instructions are clear.	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
7. Understands the texts and able to answer the questions with confidence	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
8. Session length is appropriate	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
9. Known to self that there are improvements in one or two reading skills	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0
10. Developed the love for reading	Y	Y	Y	Y	100	0

Table 13

Parents' Try-out Evaluation

Criteria	Parent Evaluator				Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	1	2	3	4		
1. The pupil attends the reading session regularly with eagerness and joy.	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
2. The pupil shows willingness to participate in the program.	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
3. The pupil is aware of his/her reading	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree

goals in participating in the program.

4. Setting promotes students' engagements for the entire session (location, room).	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
5. The content is aligned with foundational reading skills for the grade.	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
6. The text and text complexity are appropriate for the reading level of students	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
7. A sufficient amount of time is allocated for instruction and the time allocated is used effectively.	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
8. The instructional program and materials provide explicit and systematic instruction on critical reading.	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
9. The pupil is engaged and responsive.	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree
10. Improvements in one or two reading skills are evident on the pupil.	4	4	4	4	4.0	Strongly Agree

Discussion

To help struggling readers, it is crucial to identify their reading level and determine their skills where they demonstrate difficulty. To cope, students who fall at the frustration level need extra reading instruction (Allington, 2006). Riley, Alphameg, Zeemir, and Martha were some students placed at the frustration level of reading and became the student participants in this study.

Though Martha had just one skill of difficulty, vocabulary, it still affected her total reading achievement. She tended to guess the meaning of words and didn't use context clues to choose the correct meaning of the words. However, she recognized and scanned the words, resulting in her fluent reading of the passages. Alphameg received low scores on word recognition, vocabulary, and fluency. She often slowed when trying to sound individual words she could not recognize automatically. Her low scores in fluency could be attributed to her low level of word recognition skills. Riley and Zeemir scored low in all the reading skills, though each got different scores in each reading skill. This situation made Riley and Zeemir read words and texts slowly and laboriously without correct phrasing and less comprehension.

It was from this result that the proposed reading intervention program was designed and developed. **ICanRead** was conceptualized to address the needs of these struggling readers by including activities that follow the elements of effective reading instruction (National Reading Panel, 2000): word recognition (phonics and phonemic awareness), fluency, vocabulary, and text comprehension. These elements are integrated within the program's three main parts: Get Ready, Read Aloud, and Reading Skills Boost.

The researcher-facilitator tried out the program to Riley, Alphameg, Zeemir, and Martha. It was implemented individually to give more focused time on what is needed to

improve (Barbe, 1965), specifically on their identified area of difficulty. Each student was allowed to read at their level as they were being guided by reading instructions indicated in the program. **ICanRead** aims to guide, teach, and support struggling readers to improve their reading level, not to give activities and evaluate performance and label them according to their ability. It is to help guide the children through the learning process and enable them to do things they cannot do independently until they can do it themselves.

The purpose of the 'Get Ready' part is to activate the prior knowledge or schema of the learner by looking at what is already known about the passage. The student can learn new information through this reading activity by connecting the text to information already stored in their head (Miller, 2002). Through this part of the reading intervention program, Riley, Zeemir, Alphameg, and Martha have learned to use their schema to have an initial understanding of the text. By checking their prior knowledge, they would start thinking of related words in the text. And when they encounter those words, they use their schematic cueing system to read and understand the text. One example is when they went through Lesson 3, Colors of the Rainbow. One activity in the "Get Ready" part was listening to a riddle that goes like this, "*Violet, indigo and blue, red, yellow, orange and green. At the end of this object, a pot of gold can be seen. What is this?*" then each of them answered 'rainbow.' So, whenever they read the word 'rainbow,' they did it quickly, as well as the names of the rainbow colors in the text. They have enhanced their prediction skills and motivated them to go further with the passage and read.

The 'Read Aloud' part provides opportunities for the students to develop and enhance listening skills as the passage is read to them by the teacher. Listening is a critical factor in learning to read. When a learner hears a word from a story, it will add to their vocabulary bank, and when they encounter the word in a written text, they will associate it and be able to decode and read. It is also in this part of the reading intervention program that the events in the story, characters, and emotions presented are discussed. After listening to the passage, the student reads and applies what they have heard from the teacher. The teacher listens and records the unknown and challenging words. When asked to read the text *Color of the Rainbow*, Riley, Zeemir, and Alphameg know how to decode some words they hardly recognize because they have heard it first from the teacher.

The third central part of the program is the 'Reading Skills Boost' wherein the reading skills are being enhanced. It is in this part of the program that the researcher-facilitator puts more emphasis on the specific needs of the four student participants. Different strategies for word recognition, like sight word reading, word flashcards, spelling, and cards for games, are being utilized. Riley, Zeemir, and Alphameg were assisted with the unknown words from the passage noted during the Read Aloud part. One sample is with Riley. He struggled to recognize the words *decided, choose, shiny, sunset, clouds, ocean, bubble, meadow, dance, breeze, applesauce, climbing, special, almost, and anyone*. After the researcher-facilitator had noted these difficult words for Riley, she wrote them on flashcards and helped Riley read the words by assisting him in

sound and blending the letters to form the word. The same strategy was applied to Zeemir, Alphameg, and Martha. In this part of the reading intervention program, the vocabulary is expanded through different vocabulary testing techniques like cloze test, matching, sentence completion, odd one out, dictation, and definitions. In Lesson 3, with the passage *Colors of the Rainbow*, each of the student participants tried to find the odd word from the given words derived from the passage:

1. red, yellow, green, blue, candy, purple
2. clouds, sky, ocean, rainbow, sun, moon
3. trees, grass, flowers, ice cream

Each got the correct answers with the exact reasons for choosing their solution. For #1, each said that 'candy' is the odd word because it is not a color, while red, yellow, blue, and purple are colors. For #2, 'ocean' is the odd word because it is not found up in the sky, and for #3, 'ice cream' is the odd word because it is not a part of plants or kind of plant. The students learned how to analyze and understand words through testing vocabulary activities like the one mentioned above. This part of the program includes echo reading and repeated readings for fluency improvement. During the echo reading, the researcher-facilitator read a line of the text aloud, and the student read it back, matching the facilitator's emphasis and fluency. During the repeated reading, each student participant read the same passage several times, and they were timed. These two fluency activities allowed Riley, Zeemir, Alphameg, and Martha to practice the challenging words during the 'Read Aloud' part. After-reading strategies like summarizing, retelling, answering comprehension questions, recognizing sequence, comparing and contrasting, and identifying and interpreting meaning are employed for comprehension instruction. Riley, Zeemir, Alphameg, and Martha learned how to construct meaning through different comprehension strategies. See Riley's work below on comprehension (Figure 4). He could describe the rainbow in his own words and accomplished the second activity. That was how he understood the passage, likewise with Zeemir, Alphameg, and Martha.

Figure 4
Riley's Works on Comprehension

Each activity included in the reading intervention program was implemented patiently and explicitly with the researcher-facilitator's guidance and assistance. Vygotsky's scaffolding and explicit reading instruction (Miller, 2002) should be given more to students like Riley, Alphameg, Zeemir, and Martha. Each session became very meaningful to the children as they enjoyed the attention given to them. The researcher-facilitator followed the gradual release of responsibility model wherein the student learns how to do something through explicit modeling of the significant others around them, like the teacher (Miller, 2002). For example, with the learning experiences included in the *ICanRead* reading intervention program, the researcher-facilitator modeled first and explained the strategy to Riley, Zeemir, Alphameg, And Martha, then employed the guided practice where the teacher gradually allowed the student to complete their tasks with her assistance. The four students demonstrated growth and improvements in the identified skills where they found difficulty after the intervention. Zeemir made significant progress in word recognition, with a 15.9 % increase. His comprehension score was improved by a 40% increase. He gained a 20% increase in vocabulary and a 14.9 % increase in fluency. Even in the WCPM exercise, Zeemir made 26 WCPM growth. Like Zeemir, Riley scored higher in all the reading skills after the intervention. He showed improvements in word recognition with a 6.6 % increase, his comprehension was raised to 20%, his vocabulary gained a 20% increase, and his fluency score displayed a 5.6 % increase. Alphameg demonstrated improvements in her areas of difficulty: word recognition, with a 9.3% increase, and vocabulary and fluency, with a 6.8% increase, as shown in her scores, same with Martha, who gained higher scores after the treatment, including their WCPM gained scores. The students demonstrated growth in their reading assessments.

Intervention programs make a difference. It can increase reading skills for poor readers (Armbruster et al., 2010). The content of the intervention program significantly contributes to its efficacy. The instructional activities should meet the needs of the students. The use of literature in teaching reading is very effective. As stated by Cullinan, 1992 (cited in De Carlo, 1995), children learn to read by actually reading. The students are exposed to correct grammar, sentence structure, and vocabulary not used in everyday conversations through literature. Good stories stimulate the appetite of children for reading, and reading to them provides a model of skillful oral reading (Anderson et al., 1985). In this study, *ICanRead* used articles, passages, and stories in teaching reading.

The results show that the *ICanRead* intervention program produced a variety of opportunities for a positive and effective experience in literacy, specifically in learning to read. The program includes story/ article reading aloud, listening activity, echo reading, repeated reading, word recognition strategies such as word reading, word flashcards, spelling, and cards for games, vocabulary testing techniques, and comprehension strategies. These literacy activities enabled the students to develop, enhance, and exercise their reading skills. They were given the venue to practice their schema in constructing meaning and new information as they connected their early experiences and previous knowledge to the stories read (Miller, 2002). Moreover, when the students listened to stories read aloud to them, it helped them develop good listening practices,

promoting a deeper understanding of the content and improving their comprehension skills. It also provided a model of how words are correctly pronounced and passages are interpreted orally (Rasinski, 2004). During the "The Reader Reads" part, the students were given the time to read the story or passage, and during the Repeated Reading time. These strategies helped the students build accuracy and automaticity in reading words, develop prosody (appropriate phrasing and expression), and improve fluency (Rasinski, 2004). Furthermore, the activities employed in the program helped the students expand their vocabulary as they were exposed to more stories and reading passages.

The students didn't just improve their reading by measuring numbers, but they gained self-confidence and self-esteem, not just at the end of the intervention but during the process. This was confirmed through the try-out evaluation forms they have accomplished. It is significant to note that they all were willing to attend each reading session with eagerness and joy. And they knew for themselves that they improved through the program. Even the parents of the students gave a high rating for the program based on their children's experience, behavior, and progress.

Conclusion

Reading intervention programs like *ICanRead* help struggling readers to cope and progress in reading and save them from failures, especially the emphasis on addressing the specific needs of the students. It would also help researchers in the field of reading gain insights and inspire further study to enrich reading intervention programs in the country. The outcome of this study may assist school administrators and curriculum writers in planning appropriate reading instruction, developing effective intervention programs, and even authoring and publishing workbooks, textbooks, and other reading materials helpful in teaching reading. Moreover, data and facts from this study provide educators with awareness of students' abilities and the encouragement necessary to become skillful readers. It could help them provide a more pleasant atmosphere and meaningful learning experience for students in reading classes. The parents or guardians can use the strategies and the instructional materials used in the reading program at home to assist their children with reading difficulties.

Limitations of the study

The study was limited to the *ICanRead* reading intervention program; therefore, this study does not assume it would result in the same outcome for other reading programs. Data collection during the try-out was limited to the four identified struggling readers. Therefore, the design and content of the *ICanRead* reading intervention program were limited to address the needs of the four student participants. It is possible that other intervention programs could be used depending on the needs of students. Another limitation of this study is the use of instrumentation. The researcher selected the assessment tools and reading skills instrumentation. Other instruments would result differently. No measures for statistical significance have been documented since the reading intervention program was designed for this specific study.

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